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Pastoral Counselling and National Development

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Abstract

Nigeria is besieged by many ills such as social disintegration, political intolerance, tribal discrimination, violation of human rights, and insecurity. Such problems threaten the survival of the nation. It is a common experience that majority of Nigerians today are wallowing in abject poverty, penury and backwardness, while a few people live in luxury and affluence. The situation is attributed to “bad” governance among other factors. Leadership creates record of reckless plundering of the Nation’s resources for personal gains. Therefore, Nigeria is at the mercy of corrupt, tyrannical and power drunk minority. The situation has adversely affected the citizen morally, emotionally and psychologically. Scholars have discussed guidance and counseling and Pastoral counseling and psychotherapy as possible ways of solving this national menace, however, not much have been done on how Pastoral counseling can influence good governance and national development. So, there is still need to interrogate the Biblical principles of counseling and apply it to governance in Nigeria. Therefore, this paper seeks to examine the significance of Pastoral counseling in national development. The research employs the descriptive method, interviews were conducted and data collected were qualitatively analysed. Findings from the study reveal that psychotherapy contribute greatly to human development, and that pastoral counseling is a tool that enhances good governance, and therefore recommends that Christian leaders and public office holders should rise to the occasion to save the tragic situation by employing the biblical and counseling principles to condemn the causes of hardship and poverty in the society.

Keywords: Pastoral counseling, Therapy, Psychotherapy, Governance, Servant-leadership

1. Introduction

The nation building is one which involves effort of the patriotic people of a country, and its joint responsibility of every individual. The degree of involvement, however, depends on the different age-stages of the citizens of the country. For instance, people who are old cannot perform any effective role as the youth and adolescents would. Also, youth and adolescents irrespective of the agility and pro-activeness cannot occupy the place the adults and the elderly. Development is highly needed among the citizens, such as; the youth, adolescents, adults and elderly, since they are major stakeholders in the project of nation-building (Adegoke, 2003: 56). Due to this singular and crucial point, all efforts must be put in place for their physical, social, moral, mental, spiritual, educational, psychological, vocational, and personality development. In reality, it is impossible to separate one facet of development or growth from another; so interrelated and interdependent are they within the complexity of human development. Counselling is therefore required as mechanism to foster a sense of nationhood and promote national development, to ensure adaptability to promote social equality and remove divisions of race, tribe and religion; to respect

the cultural traditions of the nation, both as expressed in social institutions and relationships etc. (Adekola, 2000: 43-46).

2. Meaning of Counselling

Counselling is a process of helping people with their problems. Other synonymous names with counselling include; therapy, helping rehabilitation and others. Effective Counselling should result in desirable changes in the lives of the people with problems. Counselling thus describes processes by which a professionally trained person (a counsellor) attempts to help an individual (a client) resolve some problems. Guidance and Counselling thus describe the organized efforts of individuals or institutions to help a client achieve his potentials and the processes initiated to help him solve his or her problems so that he or she could be more effective and satisfied (Ademola, 1999: 62-64). Generally, in a guidance and counselling relationship, the Counsellor may be able to effect desirable changes in the client's perceptions, thinking, feelings, emotions and actions so that the client is, in the end, more effective and satisfied. Guidance is a family name for all the helping services within the general educational and community systems. This is why Ipaye (1983) posited that guidance on the one hand is a general label, an umbrella term that covers all the means whereby an institution identifies and responds to the individual needs of people and thereby helping the individual to develop his or her maximum potential. Counselling, on the other hand, is a subset of the general term that are called guidance.

Furthermore, Olayinka (2019) defined counselling as the process in which one person assist another in a person-to-person or face-to-face encounter. This assistance, he stressed, may take many forms: it may be educational, vocational, social, recreational, emotional and or moral. Makinde (2015) opined that counselling as "an enlightened process whereby people help each other by facilitating growth, development and positive change through an exercise of self-understanding and self-actualisation." According to Blocher (2014), it involves helping an individual become more fully aware of himself and the ways in which he's responding to the influences in his environment. It further assists him to establish some personal meaning for this behaviour and to develop and clarify a set of goals and values for future behaviour.

3. Pastoral Counselling

The pastoral counselor, through a spiritual leader should utilize a number of psychological experiential and academic strategies to rehabilitate the church member with a problem. The pastoral counsellor may begin by observing certain behaviour such as: (1) how the church youth members behave, (2) why they behave that way; (3) how to handle them; (4) how to counsel them. The implication of the above approach is that the pastoral counsellor should conduct psychological assessment of the behaviour he is observing. This means that the pastoral counsellor should know much more than the Bible. He needs adequate knowledge of psychology and other subjects such as Biology, Sociology, medicine, while he may not necessarily be an expert in these areas. Since the solution of the problem pre supposes that it has been clearly defined, adequate assessment should precede any programme of pastoral counselling.

The works of Thornburg, Walsh and Akinboye (2008) essentially outlined the basic principles of counselling, ranging from the strictly psychodynamic to the terribly behavioural:

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- i. Concerns about self (including physical appearance, peoples' perceptions, health etc).
 - ii. Morality: Drinking alcohol. Smoking and other drugs, breaking societal rules.
 - iii. Peers and friends- Concerned about being popular, utopian perfectionist beliefs, fault-finding.
 - iv. God-how to know what he wants them to do, does he listen to me, how to talk to him. What is he likes.
 - v. National and world issues- hunger, money, war.
 - vi. My future- what to do living, having enough money, how to make decision, can I get a job.
 - vii. The church- Is satisfying, should be involved in social issues, not planned for youth, need better leaders.
 - viii. Religion- Wishing to relate more personally with God, is it alright to doubt, hard to explained faith and convictions, having not enough faith etc.

Useful pastoral counselling may include programmes directed towards:

- (a) Solving personal- social problems- preaching teaching sermon- modelling talking etc. Any form of communication with the church member that leads to trust and consequently relieve his problem. At every stage, the guiding questions include how and why he behaves, how to handle him and how to help him out.
- (b) Prevention of the development of maladaptive behaviours such as drug abuse, alcoholism, smoking, conflicts, frustrations, depressions, low self- concept and anxieties
- (c) Establishing adequate vocational adjustment decision- making skills maturity, employment seeking and occupational adaptation competence.
- (d) Developing adequate work habits and creativity.
- (e) Evolving pre- marital and marital counselling programmes.
- (f) Establishment of adequate community and national awareness (Idowu, 1974: 55-59).

4. Pastoral Counselling and National Development

National development presupposes that either there has been no nation, and therefore one is envisaged and is being planned; or that one that exists has to be reconstructed in order to be worthy of the name. National development, therefore, needs a chief Architect or developer- someone who has not only a theoretical conception of what a nation should be, but is also equipped with the practical knowledge of the facts and rule that will make the building a worthy work of art as well as an abiding reality- a triumph of skillful planning and execution (Lovell, 2016: 70). He should also be a person who has regard for genuine talents and is ready to afford himself of the best of such talents in persons of suitable caliber without any prejudice with regard to places of origin or relational connections. What the developer needs in his co-workers or builders and general workers should be capacity for work, ability to understand and carry out well laid out plans, honesty and integrity (Akinboye, 2005: 57). He himself should be a dedicated person, leading dedicated co- workers- all of them together with one central aim of making the best job of their assignment; he should have appropriated the wisdom of ages that the best art of commanding is to take a fair share of work. If the master planner and those who work with him

to translate his plan into reality should become self-centered or selfish, or if they should deviate from the noble principle dictated by their goal of architecture, the result will be inevitable futility; their planned “city, a tower with its top in the heavens” will only attain the confusion of Babel (Adeyemi, 2018:60-65).

Furthermore, what are the basic materials for developing a nation? These are people, persons created and endowed with inherent freedom, which may be latent (to assert itself in due course) or is being expressed in various ways; persons with the faculties of intelligent will and purpose which develop and come into some forms of fruition in accordance with opportunities, education and development (Kalish, 2001:95). At the domestic or a single ethnic level, such personal autonomy as outlined above is prevented from excesses by what may be described as a natural community of interest. With a nation, peoples at various levels of cultures and development are brought together, or flung together, as in the case of Nigeria or other countries of Africa where it was the hand of foreign imperialism that determined which peoples should come together to form a country which they hoped would become a nation (Akinyode, 2016: 78).

This is a situation which needs very careful handling, especially when the heavy, compelling-restraining hand of imperialism is removed and the peoples of various backgrounds and levels of culture are faced with the task of settling down together, accepting leadership, developing a community of interest, and thinking of themselves, not exclusively and selfishly as belonging to this or that ethnic group (e.g. as Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba), but as belonging together as one people, all together and with sincerity seeking “the good of their Jerusalem”. A national consciousness has to be born, but not without the process of becoming – birth throes, growth and development, and conformity to the immanent norm of being. This is the inevitable rule for a nation to develop her own authentic corporate personality (Baumrind, 2019:58-61).

Paul the apostle wrote in a metaphorical language about building. This metaphor is quite relevant to the Christian, in developing the nation, Nigeria. He wrote in part,

... As a wise master-builder, I have laid the foundation and another builds thereon. But let every man take heed how he builds thereupon. For other foundation can no man lay than that which is laid, which is Jesus Christ. Now if any man build upon this foundation, gold, silver, precious stones, wood, hay, and stubble; every man’s work shall be made manifest... and the fire shall try every man’s work of what sort it is (Bryne, 2005: 87).

When fire tries materials like gold, silver, precious stones, they shall come out fire, shining than ever before. On the contrary, if fire has to try the other three materials, that is, wood, hay and stubble no doubt, nothing but may be ashes would be left. So, as Christians build on Jesus Christ who is the foundation, they are called upon to build on the entity called Nigeria as well. There is a very clear warning for the Christian. He is called upon to build with materials that endure, that is, the first three rather than the last three materials. Otherwise, he shall “suffer loss”. In developing the nation, such materials as prayers, patriotism, promotion of righteousness, discipline etc. will represent good and enduring materials (Crutchfield, .and Ballachey, 2012: 77-81). On the contrary, things like unrighteousness, lawlessness, apathy, compromises, etc. will represent materials that cannot endure or stand the test of fire. For using that former, there is a

reward, but for using the latter, there is no reward. The Christian is then enjoined to make use of the 'building materials,' that endure through time and eternity (Elegbeleye, 2021: 43-47).

Obligation of the Christian to Earnest Prayer: One great responsibility of the Nigerian Christian to the building of his nation, is fervency in prayer. Paul underscores this point when he wrote:

I exhort therefore, that, first of all, supplications, prayers intercessions, and giving of thanks, be made for all men; For kings, and for all that are in authority; that we may lead a quiet and peaceable life in all godliness and honesty (1 Tim.2;1-2).

No matter how despotic the ruler may be, the Christian has no choice but to pray for him. It does not even matter if such a ruler persecutes Christians (Elwell, 2018: 91-93).

The injunction of Jesus Christ Himself is very clear. "Love your enemies, bless them that curse you,... and pray for them which despitefully use you and persecute" (Mat. 5:44). So, any lack in this area, for the Christian, is simply, disobedience

God does not expect the ungodly or the unbeliever to pray. He expects His own people to come to Him penitently in prayer. Abogunrin (2014) puts it thus:

The healing of the sick nation is not committed to the politicians nor to the freedom fighters, but God says, it is the responsibility of His people, those who are called by His name.

The failure of Christians to engage in fervent prayers may not be unconnected with many evils being perpetrated, seemingly unrestrained in the Nigerian society. There is no limit to what the Christian can achieve, if he will take the issue of praying to God, for the nation, with all the seriousness it deserves. Rather than analyse the national problem and apportion blames alone, the Christian should pray more. One enduring material that will help Nigeria to be developed up is prayer.

In addition, Promotion of Righteous is another factor: 'Righteous exalts a nation but sin is a reproach to any people' (Prov. 14:34). True righteous involves being really obedient to the law of the land and the recognition that all men irrespective of color or race, are of one blood having been created in the image of God. It is obvious that, there is no society in which all men are on the same level. However, the Christian should be actively involved in causes that support and promote equal opportunities (Feldman & Elliot, 2014: 66-68).

In obeying the laws of the land, there is a problem that nags. What if government promulgates an unrighteous law, or a law that is not in consonance with the will of God, is the Christian obliged to obey? The apostles were confronted with a similar situation on a number of occasions. On one such occasion, they were forbidden from preaching the gospel of Jesus Christ. Peter and John had to respond bluntly, 'Whether it be right in the sight of God to hearken unto you more than unto God, judge ye. For one cannot but speak the things which we have seen and heard' (Acts 4:19-20). The Christian should not find any ambiguity, if the interest of the state clashes with that of God (Gaddis, & Brooks-Gunn, 2015: 23-25).

Patriotism and performance of civil responsibilities: quite a number of Christians are ignorant of political issues. Perhaps that explains why few committed Christians are actively involved in influencing the political process. The Christian cannot afford to be ambivalent about governments. Like it was pointed out earlier, God established government and because of this

divine origin, he cannot be apathetic towards politics. Governments are parts of God's plan (Hart, Gulbranson, & Smith, 2018: 80).

Many things are done by legislation and that underscores the reason why the Christian must be interested in the governmental processes. Somebody like Wilberforce brought an end to slave trade by making use of political power. Many others have worked tirelessly in government to see a new order emerge. Christian should take keen interest in the people that would be elected to rule him. He should familiarize himself with the candidates vying for one post or another. Then, he should exercise his voting privilege. This will go a long way in making sure that the right person who will promote the will of God being done in the country, would be chosen (Hein, 2010: 54-56).

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, national development is a task for every individual and responsibility of patriotic citizen. The counselor is in a good position to create counselling techniques about implementing life skills programs that will help people to grow and develop in their full potential. Counselors have the training to apply cognitive behavioural approaches, group processes, and other developmental strategies in the effort to improve Nigerians ability to adjust properly to crisis situation. The pastoral counsellors were therefore challenged to play their God-given role in taking part in national development, using their professional experience, technical competence and their right standing with God. Counsellors' positive contributions will help in behavior modification, adjustment mechanism and upholding the social and moral values in bring sanity into the system.

Based on the conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- a. Counsellors should play well their part in national development, using their professional experience and training
- b. Counsellors should be recognized by Government and given an enabling environment and necessary encouragement as they discharge their duties in nation-building
- c. Government should give adequate orientation to citizens on the need to seek counselling regularly.

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